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“How I Make My Students Love the Subject, Araling Panlipunan”

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For some if not for many students, especially among the millennial, the subject, “Araling Panlipunan” may not belong to their line of favorites. What could be the reasons why? This question is now answered in this article and every answer is actually based on the actual experiences of the teacher with his/her students.

Among the many reasons why not most students love the subject, “Araling Panlipunan” are: (1) so many items require memorization; (2) the ideas involved are very broad that they become not too easy to understand; (3) there are too many involved; etc. These few reasons do not include the fact that the subject does not only deal with local matters but as well as foreign ones. The study of the subject is some sort of global in coverage. Aside from being global in coverage, the study of the subject is still divided into different eras or epochs.

It seems to the majority the subject is only intended for the intelligent ones.

It is high time that all “Araling Panlipunan” teachers do something about this reality. This subject is actually an easy subject only if students will start appreciating its value. To know one’s self, he/she has to look back to his/her roots or origins. This can happen with the massive interest and the unceasing curiosity towards learning from the subject. It should therefore be instilled in students’ mind that if they want to appreciate themselves and other people as well, they should in fact love the subject, “Araling Panlipunan”.

How do I make my students love the subject, “Araling Panlipunan”? I do this by making them explore while they are learning or while I teach them. How do I make them explore? I allow them to venture first before I introduce to them the subject matter. I make them venture by pre-assigning to them the topics or the learning areas. By venturing, I let them do a self-discovery method in which they will be doing some readings, viewings, listening, interviewing, internet-searching, etc. Allowing my students to answer performance task in various ways could bring out their multiple intelligence such as writing a poem about the topic discussed, editorial cartooning for those who are good at drawing and sketching, essay writing for those who loves writing, composing “hugot” lines of what attracts them for the lesson of the day and other means of gauging their understanding of what I taught them. With these varied methods, they are certainly going to be not just interested but also properly equipped for the next day’s class discussion. Of course, this is only one among the many things that I employ in order to make my students love the subject, “Araling Panlipunan”.

“Teachers are role models; so before we can make our students love the subject we are teaching to them, we ourselves should love it first, and there should be manifestations of this love for the subject.”

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